

Quasi ξ - Normal Spaces and \square G ξ -Closed Sets

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the concept of \square g ξ -closed sets as a weak form of \square g-closed sets. By utilizing \square g ξ -closed sets, we define \square g ξ -closed, almost \square g ξ -closed, \square g ξ -continuous and almost \square g ξ -continuous functions. We also introduce the notion of quasi ξ -normal spaces and obtain a characterization and some preservation theorems for quasi ξ -normal spaces. Further we show that this property is a topological property and it is a hereditary property only with respect to closed domain subspaces. The relationships among normal, π -normal, quasi normal, softly normal, mildly normal, α -normal, $\pi\alpha$ -normal, quasi α -normal, softly α -normal, mildly α -normal, ξ -normal, $\pi\xi$ -normal, quasi ξ -normal, softly ξ -normal and mildly ξ -normal are investigated.

1. Introduction

The concept of α -open sets were introduced by Njastad [10]. The notion of quasi normal space was introduced by Zaitsev [14]. Levine [8] initiated the study of so called g-closed sets in order to extend many of the most important properties of closed sets to a large family. This concept was found to be useful and many results in general topology were improved. Singal and Singal [13] have introduced the notion of mildly normal spaces which are weaker form of quasi normal spaces due to Zaitsev [14]. Lal and Rahman [7] have further studied notions of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. Dontchev and Noiri [4] introduced the notion of \square g-closed sets as a weak form of g-closed sets due to Levine [8]. By using \square g-closed sets, Dontchev and Noiri [4] obtained a new characterization and some preservation theorems for quasi normal spaces. Devi et al. [3] introduced the concept of ξ -closed sets. Arockiarani and Janaki [1] introduced the concept of $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets as a weak form of πg -closed sets due to Dontchev and Noiri [4] and by using $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets, obtained a characterization and some preservation theorems for quasi α -normal spaces. Kalantan [6] introduced a weaker version of normality called \square -normality and proved that \square -normality is a property which lies between normality and almost normality. The notion of α -normal space was introduced by Benchalli and Patil [2]. Hamant Kumar and M. C. Sharma [12] introduced the concept of softly normal spaces and obtained its properties. Hamant Kumar [5] introduced the concept of g ξ -closed sets and by using g ξ -closed sets, obtained a characterization and some preservation theorems for ξ -normal and ξ -regular spaces.

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2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, τ) , and (Z, τ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **τ -open**. The complement of a τ -open set is said to be **τ -closed**. A is said to be **α -open** [10] if $A \subseteq int(cl(int(A)))$. The complement of a α -open set is said to be **α -closed**. The intersection of all α -closed sets containing A is called **α -closure** of A , and is denoted by **$\alpha cl(A)$** . The **α -interior** of A , denoted by **$\alpha int(A)$** , is defined as union of all α -open sets contained in A .

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space X is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [8] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is τ -open in X .
- (2) **α -generalized closed** [4] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in X .
- (3) **α -generalized closed** [9] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is τ -open in X .
- (4) **α -generalized closed** [1] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in X .
- (5) **ξ -closed** [3] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $g\alpha$ -open in X .
- (6) **g-open** (resp. **τ -g-open**, **α -g-open**, **τ - $g\alpha$ -open**, **ξ -open**) if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. τ -g-closed, α -g-closed, τ - $g\alpha$ -closed, ξ -closed).

The intersection of all ξ -closed sets containing A is called **ξ -closure** [5] of A , and is denoted by $\xi cl(A)$. The **ξ -interior** [5] of A , denoted by $\xi int(A)$, is defined as union of all ξ -open sets contained in A .

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space X is said to be

- (1) **generalized ξ -closed** (briefly **$g\xi$ -closed**) [5] if $\xi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is τ -open in X .
- (2) **α -generalized ξ -closed** if $\xi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in X .

2.3 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed as well as α -g-closed but not closed.

2.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is g -closed as well as αg -closed. It is also $g\xi$ -closed but not closed.

2.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is α -closed as well as ξ -closed but not closed.

2.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b, c\}$ is ξ -closed as well as $g\xi$ -closed but not closed.

2.8 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g\xi$ -closed but not closed.

2.9 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g\xi$ -closed but it is neither g -closed nor closed.

2.10 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\square = \{\square, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{b\}$ are πg -closed as well as $\pi g\alpha$ -closed.

3. Quasi ξ -normal spaces

3.1 Definition. A space X is said to be ξ -normal [5] (resp. α -normal [2]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint ξ -open (resp. α -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

3.2 Definition. A space X is said to be $\square\xi$ -normal (resp. \square -normal [6], $\square\alpha$ -normal) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , one of which is \square -closed, there exist disjoint ξ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

3.3 Definition. A space X is said to be quasi ξ -normal (resp. quasi normal [14], quasi α -normal [1]) if for every pair of disjoint \square -closed subsets H, K of X , there exist disjoint ξ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.

3.4 Definition. A space X is said to be mildly ξ -normal (resp. mildly normal [13], mildly α -normal [1]) if for every pair of disjoint regular closed subsets H, K of X , there exist disjoint ξ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.

3.5 Definition. A space X is said to be softly ξ -normal (resp. softly normal [12], softly α -normal) if for any two disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , one of which is \square -closed and other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint ξ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

(a) \implies (b). Let U and V be any \square -open subsets of a quasi ξ -normal space X such that $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Then, $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint \square -closed subsets of X . By quasi ξ -normality of X , there exist disjoint ξ -open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X - U \subseteq U_1$ and $X - V \subseteq V_1$. Let $G = X - U_1$ and $H = X - V_1$. Then, G and H are ξ -closed subsets of X such that $G \cap U = \emptyset$, $H \cap V = \emptyset$ and $G \cap H = X$.

(b) \implies (c). Let A be a \square -closed and B is a \square -open subsets of X such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Then, $X - A$ and B are \square -open subsets of X such that $(X - A) \cap B = X$. Then, by part (b), there exist ξ -closed sets G and H of X such that $G \subseteq (X - A)$, $H \subseteq B$ and $G \cap H = X$. Then, $A \subseteq (X - G)$, $(X - B) \subseteq (X - H)$ and $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = \emptyset$. Let $U = X - G$ and $V = (X - H)$. Then U and V are disjoint ξ -open sets such that $A \subseteq U$ and $X - V \subseteq B$. Since $X - V$ is ξ -closed, then we have $\xi\text{cl}(U) \subseteq (X - V)$. Thus, $A \subseteq U \subseteq \xi\text{cl}(U) \subseteq B$.

(c) \implies (d). Let A and B be any disjoint \square -closed subset of X . Then $A \subseteq X - B$, where $X - B$ is \square -open. By the part (c), there exists a ξ -open subset U of X such that $A \subseteq U \subseteq \xi\text{cl}(U) \subseteq X - B$. Let $V = X - \xi\text{cl}(U)$. Then, V is a ξ -open subset of X . Thus, we obtain $A \subseteq U$, $B \subseteq V$ and $\xi\text{cl}(U) \cap \xi\text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(d) \implies (a). It is obvious.

3.11 Proposition. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function, then:

- (a) The image of ξ -open subset under an open continuous function is ξ -open.
- (b) The inverse image of ξ -open (resp. ξ -closed) subset under an open continuous function is \square - ξ -open (resp. ξ -closed) subset.
- (c) The image of ξ -closed subset under an open and a closed continuous surjective function is ξ -open.

3.12 Theorem. The image of a quasi ξ -normal space under an open continuous injective function is a quasi ξ -normal.

Proof. Let X be a quasi ξ -normal space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open continuous injective function. We need to show that $f(X)$ is a quasi ξ -normal. Let A and B be any two disjoint \square -closed sets in $f(X)$. Since the inverse image of a \square -closed set under an open continuous function is a \square -closed. Then, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint \square -closed sets in X . By quasi ξ -normality of X , there exist ξ -open subsets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is an open continuous injective function, we have $A \subseteq f(U)$, $B \subseteq f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. By **Proposition 3.11**, we obtain $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint ξ -open sets in $f(X)$ such that $A \subseteq f(U)$ and $B \subseteq f(V)$. Hence $f(X)$ is quasi ξ -normal.

From the above theorem, we have the following corollary.

3.13 Corollary. Quasi \square - ξ -normality is a topological property.

The following lemma helps us to show that quasi ξ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

3.14 Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If A is a ξ -open set in X , then $A \cap M$ is ξ -open set in M .

3.15 Theorem. Quasi ξ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

Proof. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a quasi ξ -normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint \square -closed sets in M . Since M is a closed domain subspace of X , then we have A and B be any disjoint \square -closed sets of X . By quasi ξ -normal of X , there exist disjoint ξ -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. By the **Lemma 3.14**, we obtain $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint ξ -open sets in M such that $A \subseteq U \cap M$ and $B \subseteq V \cap M$. Hence, M is quasi ξ -normal subspace.

Since every closed and open (clopen) subset is a closed domain, then we have the following corollary.

4. Preservation Theorems

The following result is useful for giving some other characterizations of quasi ξ -normal spaces.

4.1 Lemma. A subset A of a space X is $\square g\xi$ -open if and only if $F \subseteq \xi \text{int}(A)$ whenever $F \subseteq A$ and F is \square -closed.

4.2 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is quasi ξ -normal.
- (b) For any disjoint \square -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $g\xi$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.
- (c) For any disjoint \square -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $\square g\xi$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.
- (d) For any \square -closed set H and any \square -open set V containing H , there exists a $g\xi$ -open set U of X such that $H \subseteq U \subseteq \xi \text{cl}(U) \subseteq V$.
- (e) For any \square -closed set H and any \square -open set V containing H , there exists a $\square g\xi$ -open set U of X such that $H \subseteq U \subseteq \xi \text{cl}(U) \subseteq V$.

Proof. (a) \square (b), (b) \square (c), (c) \square (d), (d) \square (e) and (e) \square (a).

(a) \square (b). Let X be quasi ξ -normal space. Let H, K be disjoint \square -closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint ξ -open sets U, V such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$. Since every ξ -open set is $g\xi$ -open, U and V are $g\xi$ -open sets such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.

(b) \square (c): Let H, K be two disjoint \square -closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint $g\xi$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$. Since every $g\xi$ -open set is $\square g\xi$ -open, U and V are $\square g\xi$ -open sets such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.

(c) \square (d): Let H be any \square -closed set and V be any \square -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist disjoint $\square g\xi$ -open sets U and W such that $H \subseteq U$ and $X - V \subseteq W$.

W. By **Lemma 4.1**, we get $X - V \subseteq \xi_{int}(W)$ and $\xi_{cl}(U) \subseteq \xi_{int}(W) = \emptyset$. Hence $H \subseteq U \subseteq \xi_{cl}(U) \subseteq X - \xi_{int}(W) \subseteq V$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e): Let H be any \square -closed set and V be any \square -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist $g\xi$ -open set U of X such that $H \subseteq U \subseteq \xi_{cl}(U) \subseteq V$. Since, every $g\xi$ -open set is $\square g\xi$ -open, there exists $\square g\xi$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subseteq U \subseteq \xi_{cl}(U) \subseteq V$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a): Let H, K be any two disjoint \square -closed sets of X . Then $H \subseteq X - K$ and $X - K$ is \square -open. By assumption, there exists $\square g\xi$ -open set G of X such that $H \subseteq G \subseteq \xi_{cl}(G) \subseteq X - K$. Put $U = \xi_{int}(G)$, $V = X - \xi_{cl}(G)$. Then U and V are disjoint ξ -open sets of X such that $H \subseteq U$ and $K \subseteq V$.

4.3 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

(a) **ξ -closed [3]** (resp. **$\square g\xi$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is ξ -closed (resp. $\square g\xi$ -closed) in Y for every closed set F of X .

(b) **rc-preserving [11]** (resp. **almost closed [13]**, **almost ξ -closed**, **almost $\square g\xi$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is regular closed (resp. closed, ξ -closed, $\square g\xi$ -closed) in Y for every $F \in RC(X)$.

(c) **\square -continuous [4]** (resp. **almost \square -continuous [4]**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is \square -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

(d) **almost continuous [13]** if $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X for every regular open set V of Y .

(e) **$\square g\xi$ -continuous** (resp. **almost $\square g\xi$ -continuous**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\square g\xi$ -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

4.4 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost \square -continuous and $\square g\xi$ -closed function, then $f(A)$ is $\square g\xi$ -closed in Y for every $\square g\xi$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be any $\square g\xi$ -closed set of X and V be any \square -open set of Y containing $f(A)$. Since f is almost \square -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is \square -open in X and $A \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, we have $\xi_{cl}(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f(\xi_{cl}(A)) \subseteq V$. Since f is $\square g\xi$ -closed, $f(\xi_{cl}(A))$ is $\square g\xi$ -closed in Y and hence we obtain $\xi_{cl}(f(A)) \subseteq \xi_{cl}(f(\xi_{cl}(A))) \subseteq V$. Hence $f(A)$ is $\square g\xi$ -closed in Y .

4.5 Theorem. A surjection $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost $\square g\xi$ -closed if and only if for each subset S of Y and each $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$, there exists a $\square g\xi$ -open set V of Y such that $S \subseteq V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq U$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that f is almost $\square g\xi$ -closed. Let S be a subset of Y and $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$. If $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a $\square g\xi$ -open set of Y such that $S \subseteq V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq U$.

Sufficiency. Let F be any regularly closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \in (X - F)$ and $(X - F) \in RO(X)$. There exists a $\square g\xi$ -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subseteq V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq (X - F)$. Therefore, we have $f(F) \subseteq (Y - V)$ and $F \subseteq X - f^{-1}(V) \subseteq f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence we obtain $f(F) \subseteq Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is $\square g\xi$ -closed in Y , which shows that f is almost $\square g\xi$ -closed.

4.6 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $g\xi$ -continuous, rc-preserving injection and Y is quasi ξ -normal then X is quasi ξ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint \square -closed sets of X . Since f is an rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint \square -closed sets of Y . Since Y is quasi ξ -normal, there exist disjoint ξ -open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subseteq U$ and $f(B) \subseteq V$.

Now if $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are regularly open sets such that $f(A) \subseteq G$ and $f(B) \subseteq H$. Since f is almost $g\xi$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are disjoint $g\xi$ -open sets containing A and B which shows that X is quasi ξ -normal.

4.7 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is \square -continuous, almost ξ -closed surjection and X is quasi ξ -normal space then Y is ξ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint \square -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi ξ -normal, there exist disjoint ξ -open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq V$.

Let $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regularly open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq H$. Now, we set $K = Y - f(X-G)$ and $L = Y - f(X-H)$. Then K and L are ξ -open sets of Y such that $A \subseteq K$, $B \subseteq L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subseteq G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subseteq H$. Since G and H are disjoint, K and L are disjoint. Since K and L are ξ -open and we obtain $A \subseteq \xi\text{int}(K)$, $B \subseteq \xi\text{int}(L)$ and $\xi\text{int}(K) \cap \xi\text{int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is ξ -normal.

4.8 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost \square -continuous and almost $g\xi$ -closed surjection. If X is quasi ξ -normal space then Y is quasi ξ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint \square -closed sets of Y . Since f is almost \square -continuous, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint \square -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi ξ -normal, there exist disjoint ξ -open sets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq V$.

Put $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regularly open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq H$. By **Theorem 4.5**, there exist $g\xi$ -open sets K and L of Y such that $A \subseteq K$, $B \subseteq L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subseteq G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subseteq H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L by **Lemma 4.1**, $A \subseteq \xi\text{int}(K)$, $B \subseteq \xi\text{int}(L)$ and $\xi\text{int}(K) \cap \xi\text{int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is quasi ξ -normal.

4.9 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and almost closed surjection and X is a normal space, then Y is quasi ξ -normal.

Proof. Since every almost closed function is almost $g\xi$ -closed by **Theorem 4.8**, Y is quasi ξ -normal.

REFERENCES

1. Arockiarani and C. Janaki, $g\alpha$ -closed sets and quasi α -normal spaces, Acta Ciencia

- Indica, Vol. XXXIII M. No. 2, (2007), 657-666.
2. S. S. Benchalli and P. G. Patil, Some new continuous maps in topological spaces, Journal of Advanced Studies in Topology 2/1-2, (2009), 53-63.
 3. R. Devi, S. N. Rajappriya, K. Muthukumaraswamy and H. Maki, ξ -closed sets in topological spaces and digital planes, Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae Online, (2006), 615-631.
 4. J. Dontchev and T. Noiri, Quasi-normal spaces and \square -g-closed sets, Acta Math. Hungar. **89**(3)(2000), 211-219.
 5. HamantKumar, ξ -normal and ξ -regular spaces in topological spaces, Int. J. Sci., Eng. And Research, Vol. 5, Issue 9, (2017), 6-10.
 6. L. Kalantan, \square -normal topological spaces, Filomat, Vol. 22 No. 1 (2008), 173-181.
 7. S. Lal and M. S. Rahman, A note on quasi-normal spaces, Indian J. Math., **32**(1990), 87-94.
 8. N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo (2),**19**(1970), 89-96.
 9. H. Maki, R. Devi and K. Balachandran, Associated topologies of generalized α -open and α -generalized closed, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Uni. Math. **15**(1994), 51-63.
 10. O. Njastad, On some class of nearly open sets, Pacific. J. Math., **15**(1965), 961.
 11. T. Noiri, Mildly normal spaces and some functions, Kyungpook Math. J. **36**(1996), 183-190.
 12. M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar, Softly normal topological spaces, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XLI M. No. 2, (2015), 81-84.
 13. M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, Mildly normal spaces, Kyungpook Math. J. **13**(1973), 27-31.
 14. V. Zaitsev, On certain classes of topological spaces and their biocompactifications, Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR, **178**(1968), 778-779.